

to the air oxidation of iodide, which gives high results. 5 mg of iodide covers the range of quinone determined in the present work.

Under suitable conditions, hydroquinone can be quantitatively oxidized to quinone by iodine⁸. The small amount of acetic acid (optimum 0.1-0.5 ml of 4 N acetic acid) must be added before the addition of acetate (optimum 5 ml of 2 N sodium acetate) to prevent the aerial oxidation of some of hydroquinone in alkaline solution. It was found that 5 ml of 0.12% iodine solution is essential for rapid and quantitative oxidation of up to 1 mg of hydroquinone. Any iodine left in the aqueous phase would cause high results and hence must be removed by washing the aqueous phase with chloroform.

The iodate waves were best recorded at pH 9.3¹⁰ with a half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) of -1.24 V. The blank runs gave iodate waves of 0.6 and 0.9 cm height using a sensitivity of 2.5×10^{-6} A/mm.

The working procedures finally developed were applied to the analysis of solutions as dilute as 1.2×10^{-6} M quinone and 1.8×10^{-6} M hydroquinone. The accuracy and precision (3 replicates) of the method were checked. Results given in Table 1 indicate the reliability of the method.

TABLE 1—MICRODETERMINATION OF QUINONE AND HYDROQUINONE BY DIFFERENTIAL PULSE POLAROGRAPHY

Quinone Taken	Quinone Found*	Relative error %	SD %	Hydroquinone Taken	Hydroquinone Found*	Relative error %	SD %
2	1.9	-5.0	5.3	3	2.9	-3.3	3.9
5	4.9	-2.0	3.8	5	4.9	-2.0	3.2
10	10.1	+1.0	1.2	10	9.9	-1.0	1.6
100	99.9	-0.1	0.2	100	100.5	+0.5	0.3
1000	996.8	-0.3	0.5	1000	997.8	-0.2	0.4

* Mean of 3 determinations.

Acknowledgement

The authors sincerely thank Mr. M. A. Sheat, for his help in preparation and purification of quinone.

References

1. S. N. SUSLOV and D. I. STOM, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1978, 33, 1423.
2. Y. A. GAWARGIOUS and S. W. BISHARA, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1969, 245, 366.
3. T. A. SMIRNOVA, YU. P. BRYVIN and B. P. YATSENEKO, *Proizvod. Khim. Prom-sti.*, 1977, 4, 44; *Anal. Abs.*, 1979, 36, 3085.
4. V. D. BEZUGLYL and V. N. DMITRIEVA, *Zavodskaya Lab.*, 1958, 24, 941; *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, 54, 11539i.
5. J. W. HAMILTON and A. L. TAPPEL, *J. Amer. Oil Chemist's Soc.*, 1963, 40, 52; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 58, 10498f.
6. H. BERG and K. KRAMARCZYK, *Talanta*, 1965, 12, 1127.
7. A. BERKA, J. VULTERIN and J. ZVKA, *Chemist Analyst*, 1962, 51, 88.
8. I. M. KOLTHOFF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1957, Vol. 3, p. 396.

9. W. GEILMANN and H. BARTLINGEK, *Mikrochemie*, 1942, 30, 217.
10. Y. M. TEMERK, M. E. AHMED and M. M. KAMAL, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1980, 301, 414.
11. G. G. RAO and T. P. SASTRI, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1958, 163, 263.
12. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", 2nd Edn., Chapman and Hall, London, 1952, Vol. 1, p. 362.

Synthesis of New Quinazolin-4-One Derivatives as Possible Antifertility/Anthelmintic Agents

Y. D. KULKARNI*, S. H. R. ABDI

and

B. KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 12 May 1982, accepted 16 February 1983

SIGNIFICANT anti-implantation activity among triphenyl ethylene moiety in a rigid frame-work having methoxy groups and/or basic amine residues as in dihydronaphthalene^{1,2}, chromans^{3,4}, indoles^{5,6}, benzofurans⁷, quinazolones⁸ provided the necessary lead for the syntheses of 2-phenyl-3-(3'-aminomethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-quinazolinones (III) and 2-phenyl/3,4,5-trimethoxy phenyl-3-(2'-methoxy/3',4',5'-trimethoxy phenyl)-6-substituted quinazolin-4-ones (IV) as possible antifertility agents.

Further, high anthelmintic activity exhibited by substituted quinazolones⁹⁻¹² tempted the authors to screen these compounds for this activity as well.

4-Aminophenol and 2-phenyl benzoxazine (I) were condensed at 170-80° to yield 2-phenyl-3-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)-quinazolin-4-one (II) which was subjected to Mannich reaction to yield III (Scheme 1). Six benzoxazines (I₁₋₆) were condensed with aromatic amines to yield IV (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. Reactions were followed by tlc. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and nmr spectra were run on a Varian A-60D instrument using TMS as the internal standard.

6-Substituted-2-aryl benzoxazine-2-ones (Table 1; I₁₋₆) were prepared according to published procedure^{1,3}.

2-Phenyl-3-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)-quinazolin-4-one (II): 2-Phenyl-benzoxazine-4-one (I₁, 2.23 g; 0.01 mole) and 4-aminophenol (1.1 g; 0.01 mole) were heated on an oil bath at 160-80° for 1/2 hr. The residue was crystallized from aqueous ethanol,

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—6-SUBSTITUTED-2-ARYL BENZOXAZINE-4-ONES (I)

Sl. No.	X	Ar	m.p. °C
I ₁	H	Phenyl	118-19
I ₂	H	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	170-72
I ₃	Br	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	134-36
I ₄	I	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	161-63
I ₅	Br	Phenyl	205-7
I ₆	I	Phenyl	160-62

* Unknown compounds.

Analytical results were satisfactory within experimental errors. IR spectra showed bands at 1140 cm⁻¹ (—OCH₃), 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic), 1760 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl of cyclic lactone), 2960 cm⁻¹ (O—H).

yield 80%, m.p. 232°. IR (KBr) 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic), 1650 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl group of cyclic amide) and 3300 cm⁻¹ (hydroxyl).

2-Phenyl-3-(4'-hydroxy-3'-aminomethyl)-quinazolin-4-ones (Table 2; III₁₋₈): II (0.001 mole) and formalin (0.002 mole) were refluxed in ethanol (25 ml) for 1 hr. A secondary amine (0.01 mole) was added and the reaction mixture further refluxed for 4-6 hr. Ethanol was distilled off and the residue was crystallized from the appropriate solvent, yield 60-80%.

2-Aryl-3-(substituted phenyl)-6-substituted quinazolin-4-ones (Table 3; IV₁₋₁₀): I (0.005 mole) was heated with appropriate primary aromatic amine (0.005 mole) on an oil bath at 150-60° for 1 hr.

TABLE 2—2-PHENYL-3-(4'-HYDROXY-3'-AMINOMETHYL)-QUINAZOLIN-4-ONES (III)

Sl. No.	NR	m.p. °C
III ₁	Dimethylamino-	195-97
III ₂	Diethylamino-	169-71(d)
III ₃	N-Phenylpiperazino	170-72
III ₄	N-Methylpiperazino	170-72
III ₅	Morpholino	102-3
III ₆	Piperidino	130-32
III ₇	4-Methylpiperidino	170-72
III ₈	Pyrolidino-	170-71

Analytical results were satisfactory within experimental errors.

IR spectra bands at 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic), 1680 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl of cyclic amide), 2980 cm⁻¹ (O—H), 3250 cm⁻¹ (broad OH).

* PMR (CDCl₃) exhibited signals at 8.2τ (4H, pentet) and 7.61τ (4H, broad triplet) of pyrrolidine; 6.28τ (2H, singlet, 3'-methylene), 4.29τ (1H, broad multiplet, 4'-hydroxy, vanishes on deuterium exchange), 3.38τ (3H, multiplet, 2',5', and 6'-aromatic protons); 2.91τ (5H, multiplet, 2-phenyl), 2.63τ (2H, multiplet, aromatic protons at 6 and 7), 2.39τ (1H, multiplet aromatic proton at 8), 1.87τ (1H, multiplet, aromatic proton at 5).

The residue obtained on cooling was refluxed with animal charcoal and the product crystallized from ethanol in yields ranging from 60-75%.

TABLE 3—2-ARYL-3-(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL)-6-SUBSTITUTED QUINAZOLIN-4-ONES (IV)

Sl. No.	X	Ar	Ar'	m.p. °C
IV ₁	H	Phenyl	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	240-41
IV ₂	Br	"	"	204-05
IV ₃	I	"	"	200-02
IV ₄	H	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	"	211-13
IV ₅	Br	"	"	205-06
IV ₆	I	"	"	168-70
IV ₇	Br	"	4-Methoxyphenyl	112-15
IV ₈	Br	"	2-Methoxyphenyl	140-42
IV ₉	I	"	2-Methoxyphenyl	150-53
IV ₁₀	I	"	4-Methoxyphenyl	175-76

Analytical results were satisfactory within experimental errors. IR spectra showed bands at 1140 cm⁻¹ (O—CH₃), 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic), 1660 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl of cyclic amide), 2950 cm⁻¹ (O—H).

* PMR (CDCl₃) exhibited signals at 6.25τ (18H, singlet, methoxy), 3.1τ (2H, multiplet, aromatic protons of Ar'), 2.6τ (2H, multiplet aromatic protons of Ar); 2.1τ (2H multiplet aromatic protons of 6,7), 1.4τ (2H, multiplet, aromatic protons at 5,8).

Biological screening: Method of Kamboj¹⁴ was used to evaluate anti-implantation activity while anthelmintic activity was assessed against *H. nana* following the procedure of Whitlock¹⁵.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head, Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow for facilities, Dr. V. P. Kamboj and Dr. J. C. Katiyar, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for biological screening of the compounds.

One of the authors (S. H. R. A.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. D. LEDNICER, J. C. BABCOCK, S. C. LYSER and G. W. DUNCAN, *Chem. Ind.*, 1963, 408.
2. D. LEDNICER, S. C. LYSER and G. W. DUNCAN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1967, 10, 78.
3. R. W. J. CARNEY, W. L. BENCZE, J. WOJTKUNSKI, A. A. RENZI, L. DORFMAN and G. DESTEVENS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, 9, 516.
4. S. RAY, P. K. GROVER, V. P. KAMBOJ, B. S. SETTY, A. B. KAR and NITYA NAND, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1976, 19, 276.
5. R. N. IYER and R. GOPALCHARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 520.
6. J. K. LANDQUIST and C. J. MORSDEN, *Chem. Ind.*, 1966, 1032.
7. P. K. GROVER, H. P. S. CHAWLA, NITYA NAND, V. P. KAMBOJ and A. B. KAR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 720.
8. S. K. SAKSENA and A. S. NADKARNI, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1971, 59, 1109.
9. E. C. TAYLOR and J. BERTULIN, *U. S. Patent*, 1969, 2,476, 756; *Chem. Abs.*, 72, 43718a.
10. R. J. ALAIZO and C. J. HALTOR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 108.
11. A. MACKEI and A. L. MISHRA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3918.
12. A. MACKEI and A. L. MISHRA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4430.
13. A. SAMMOUR, A. F. M. FAHMY and M. MAHMOOD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 222.
14. V. P. KAMBOJ, A. B. KAR, R. GOPALCHARI and R. N. IYER, *Indian J. Exptl. Biol.*, 1975, 13, 79.
15. J. H. WHITLOCK, *J. Parasitology*, 1943, 42, 29.

Chemical Investigation of Indian Medicinal Plants Possessing Anticancer Activity : Roots of *Euphorbia tirucalli* Linn.

R. K. BASLAS* and N. C. GUPTA

Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Govt. Raza P. G. College, Rohilkhand University, Rampur-244 901

Manuscript received 19 February 1982, accepted 16 February 1983

EUPHORBIA tirucalli Linn. (Euphorbiaceae), a woody climber, is widely cultivated in Indian

gardens for decorative purposes. The juice of the plant is useful in abdominal troubles, tumors, asthma and leucorrhoea¹. The milky latex is vesicant, rubefacient, purgative and carminative². The root of this plant is reported to possess anticancer activity³. The stem and milky latex of the plant have been examined for a number of compounds by different workers⁴⁻⁶. But roots of this plant have not been investigated for their chemical constituents. This is the first report on chemical examination of the roots of this plant.

Experimental

The air dried powdered roots of the plant were extracted with light petroleum ether (60-80°) under reflux. The yellow-green extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to get a resinous mass. This semi solid mass was fractionated into ethanol soluble (*Fraction 1*) and ethanol insoluble (*Fraction 2*) portions.

Fraction 1 was separated into five compounds, A, B, C, D and E by column chromatography using silica gel G as adsorbent in the solvent system benzene-ether (19 : 1).

Three compounds, F, G and H have been separated from fraction 2 on silica gel column in the system cyclohexane : ethyl acetate (4 : 1).

All the above compounds were identified by co-tlc and their identification have been confirmed by their spectroscopic studies with authentic references (Table 1).

The co-carcinogenic activity of the root of this plant is due to the presence of diterpenephorbol and resiniferonol derivatives.

TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS ISOLATED FROM ROOTS OF *Euphorbia tirucalli* LINN.

Sl. No.	Compound	hR _f value		Methods of identification	Ref.
		Observed	Authentic		
A.	24-Methylene cycloartenol	19	20	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 122°, m.m.p., ir, pmr and ms.	7
B.	Euphorbol	36	35	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, m.m.p., ir, pmr and ms.	8
C.	Euphorbol hexacosanoate	70	70	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, m.m.p., ir and ms.	9
D.	n-Hexacosanol	56	56	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, m.m.p. and ir.	10
E.	12-Deoxyphorbol-13-O-phenylacetate-16-O- α -methyl butyrate-20-acetate	70	71	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, ir, pmr and ms.	11
F.	Tinyaxoxin	30	30	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, ir, uv and ms.	✓12
G.	Taraxerone	86	86	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, m.m.p. and ir.	12
H.	20-O-Acetylrresiniferonol-9,13,14-orthophenyl acetate	32	32	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, ir, pmr and ms.	✓14

* Author for correspondence.